

MICRO-METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF NICOTINE GROUP OF ALKALOIDS IN TOBACCO PLANTS

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A new micro-method, based on the cyanogen bromide and aniline colour reaction, has been developed for the estimation of nicotine and other pyridine alkaloids in the distillate of tobacco leaves. By this method μ g. of nicotine per c.c. could be easily estimated by using a photo-electric colorimeter.

The recovery of nicotine was estimated to be 96 to 98%. For complete recovery of nicotine from a small quantity of leaves etc., a minimum of 300 c.c. of distillate requires to be collected.

In literature various methods, such as titration method, silicotungstic acid method etc., have been prescribed for estimation of nicotine group of alkaloids in tobacco plants ("Chemists' Year Book," 1951, p. 1171; "Official Methods of Analysis of A.O.A.C.," 7th Edition, 1950, p. 69). Since these methods require about 2.5-10 g. of tobacco leaves for estimation of these alkaloids, they are not suitable for micro-estimation of nicotine alkaloids needed for the study of the biogenesis of these alkaloids by culture work *in vitro* with leaf, stem and root slices. It is therefore felt necessary to devise a suitable micro-method by which a few mg. of leaves, stems or roots could be used for estimating the nicotine content. The present paper embodies an account of such a method based on photocolorimetric estimation.

Koenig (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1904, 69, 105; 1905, 70, 19) obtained a coloured compound by reacting pyridine nucleus with cyanogen bromide and a primary or a secondary amine. On the basis of this colour reaction an accurate method for estimation of nicotinic acid and its different derivatives had been developed by Swaminathan (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1942, 30, 397; Melnick, *Cereal Chem.*, 1942, 19, 553) and other workers by using cyanogen bromide and aniline. It was therefore considered desirable to explore the possibility of utilisation of the above cyanogen bromide and aniline method also for the micro-estimation of nicotine group of alkaloids in different parts of tobacco plants.

EXPERIMENTA

Comparative Study of Nicotine Content of dry Tobacco Leaves by Titration and the New Micro-method

Two sets of experiments were first arranged to assess the suitability of this method for nicotine estimations. In one set the nicotine was distilled off from 2.5 g. of tobacco leaves mixed with 25 c.c. of 1% NaOH solution and the nicotine content of the distillate was collected in 5 c.c. of $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$, and estimated by back titration against $N/10\text{-NaOH}$. In another set the distillate was collected in 5 c.c. of 1:1 HCl and the nicotine content was determined by using cyanogen bromide and aniline colour reaction in the following way.

To 1 c.c. of the distillate were added 1 c.c. of 50% sodium acetate buffer, adjusted to pH 7, 2 c.c. of 2% aqueous aniline solution (aniline freshly prepared), followed by 12 c.c. of cyanogen bromide solution. These were mixed well and allowed to stand for 10 minutes, during which period the maximum intensity of colour was obtained. This colour was then matched against a standard prepared in the same way by taking 1 c.c. solution containing 100 to 150 $\mu g.$ of nicotine. As the colour was very intense, the visual colorimeter could be used for comparison.

The results of estimation by titration and the present colorimetric method, as presented in Table I, show that percentage of nicotine alkaloids estimated by these methods compares favourably.

TABLE I

[Figures represent the average of six estimations in each batch].

Batch No.	Tobacco leaves taken.	Distillate collected over acid.	Method of estimation.	% Nicotine estimated.
A	2.5 g.	500 c.c. in 5 c.c. of $N/10$ H_2SO_4	Titration	3.2
B	2.5	500 c.c. in 1 c.c. of 1:1 HCl	Visual colorimetric	3.0

Less amounts of leaves (40 mg. to 500 mg.) were then taken and the nicotine content of the distillates (total volume 500 c.c.) estimated colorimetrically by using Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter.

TABLE II

Values of nicotine in small amount of tobacco leaves estimated by photoelectric colorimeter.

[The values represent averages of six sets of experiments in each batch].

Batch No.	Tobacco leaves taken.	Conc. of nicotine standard per c.c.	% Nicotine found.
A	500 mg.	20-40 $\mu g.$	3.06
B	200	5-10	2.96
C	40	2-4	3.0

The results presented in Table II show that by this new method 2 to 2.5 $\mu g.$ of nicotine per c.c. of distillate collected from 40 mg. of leaves could be easily estimated by using photoelectric colorimeter. For lower concentrations below 2 $\mu g.$ per c.c., the intensity of the colour developed was too faint to obtain a wider range of deflection in the scale of the galvanometer. Addition of 2 mg. of nicotine to both the standard and the unknown solutions intensified the colour, and by this "intensification" process nicotine content even below 2 $\mu g.$ per c.c. could be easily estimated. If a Multiflex galvanometer (B Lange type) is available in hand then this intensification process is not necessary and the faint colour developed by nicotine below 2 $\mu g.$ will afford a large deflection in 1:100 scale of the galvanometer.

Recovery of Added Nicotine

Further accuracy of the method was tested by determining the percentage recovery of nicotine added along with tobacco leaves and distilled off in the usual way. In batch A only 1 mg. of nicotine was distilled and the percentage recovery of nicotine evaluated. In batch B, 1 mg. of nicotine added along with 40 mg. of leaf sample was distilled and the total recovery of nicotine estimated. The total recovery less 1.2 mg. (nicotine content of 40 mg. leaf sample) gave the recovery of 1 mg. added nicotine. From the results of Table III it would appear that 96 to 98% recovery of the added nicotine (1 mg. along with 40 mg. leaf samples) could be assessed by this method.

TABLE III

Recovery of added nicotine by cyanogen bromide method.

[The values represent the average of six experiments in each batch].

Batch No.	Tobacco leaves taken.	Nicotine added.	Recovery of total nicotine.	Recovery of added nicotine.	% Recovery of added nicotine.
A.	Nil	1 mg.	0.98 mg.	0.98 mg.	98
B.	40 mg. leaves containing 1.2 mg. of nicotine.	1	2.16	0.96	96

Minimum Distillate to be collected.—In all the previous experiments 500 c.c. distillate was collected to ensure complete distillation of nicotine. In view of the long time required for the collection of such a large volume of distillate some experiments were made to assess the minimum amount of distillate to be collected for maximum recovery of nicotine. Samples of 1 mg. nicotine, 40 mg. leaves, and 40 mg. leaves plus 1 mg. nicotine were subjected to steam-distillation as before and the distillates were collected to different volumes ranging from 100 to 500 c.c. The results are presented in Table IV.

TABLE IV

% Recovery of nicotine in different volumes of distillates.

[The figures for each batch represent the average of three estimations].

Batch No.	Tobacco leaves taken.	Amount of extra nicotine added	Distillate collected.	Total recovery of nicotine.	% Nicotine recovered.
A	40 mg. of tobacco leaves containing 1.2 mg. of nicotine.	Nil	200 c.c.	0.94 mg.	72
B	Do	...	300	1.18	98
C	Do	...	400	1.14	95
D	Do	...	500	1.18	98
E	Do	1 mg.	200	1.43	65
F	Do	"	300	2.16	98
G	Do	"	400	2.14	97
H	Do	"	500	2.16	98
I	Nil	"	200	0.62	62
J	Nil	"	300	1.02	102

The results presented in Table IV clearly indicate that at the distillate volume of 100 to 200 c.c., the recovery of nicotine is only limited to 60-70%. Full recovery was made with the minimum volume of 300 c.c. of the distillate, an observation in contradiction to Ganz (*Bot. Gaz.*, 1951, 113, 195) who mentioned that nicotine was fully recovered even when the distillate was collected to 150-200 c.c.

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